

Krushi Seva E-Commerce

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Abstract:- The program is a web-based platform that aims to provide farmers with easy and cost-effective solutions to purchase pesticides, herbicides, herbicide toilets and other agricultural products. Using a combination of PHP, MySQL, JavaScript and HTML, the platform keeps costs under control while providing farmers access to quality agricultural products. The main goal of the project is to increase affordability, quality and availability in Essen. It is a solid foundation that aims to enable farmers to make informed decisions that will further increase productivity by developing affordable, efficient and effective methods. More importantly, the platform provides a reasonable price allowing farmers to access

Keywords:- Partners, Agriculture, Farmers' Response, Government, Krushi.

I. INTRODUCTION

[1]Agriculture[1] Agriculture is the lifeblood of our civilization and faces constant challenges in finding essential products in a sustainable economy. In response to these challenges, a revolutionary project was created that was a combination of PHP, MySQL, JavaScript, and HTML. The main aim of the program is to support farmers who care for our food. The constant dilemma of establishing a balanced relationship between affordable prices and quality products in the supply of agricultural inputs is at the forefront of the project. As farmers work to grow crops and ensure global food security, they often find themselves facing financial insecurity and the need for reliable supplies. [7]

Agriculture has also developed over the years. Ancient farmers tilled small amounts of land by hand, using axes and digging sticks to plant trees and create soil. At the same time, advanced bone, stone, copper and metal agricultural tools were created. New storage systems are constantly emerging. When there was a famine, people started storing food in jars and clay pots. They also began to make clay pots and other containers for carrying and cooking food. Around 5500 BC, farmers in Mesopotamia developed simple water systems. By

diverting water from streams onto farmland, farmers are able to create land once thought unsuitable for agriculture. In Mesopotamia, Egypt, and China, people studied and worked together to build and maintain better water systems.

[8] Early farmers also developed many plants. For example, around 6000 BC, various types of rice appeared in South Asia and Egypt. It is stronger than previous grains, its shell is removed more easily and it can be made into bread.

➤ Problem Statement

• Why choose a farm e-commerce site?

Farmers need agricultural ecommerce sites for easy access to a wide range of agricultural products, efficient purchasing, and the ability to make informed decisions. These platforms, which have userfriendly interfaces and mobile usability, provide businesses with time savings and security.

• Why is agricultural e-commerce better?

The advantage of agricultural ecommerce is simplicity, cost effectiveness, product diversity and user power.

• Who will benefit from the Krushi Seva website initiative?

Krushi Seva website has many good features for farmers and agriculture. First, it provides farmers with a platform for a variety of agricultural services and products, including crop management information, business information and products for good agricultural use. This centralized service provides convenience and saves time for farmers who do not need to visit multiple locations.

II. I.FEATURES / FUNCTIONALITIES OF PROJECT

A. Features of Krushi-Seva:

➤ User-friendly interface::

Krushi Seva has an intuitive user interface that allows farmers of all skill levels to easily navigate the platform.

- *User-Friendly Interface:*

The platform has an intuitive and easy-to-use interface, allowing users to easily access and use the services, regardless of their digital experience.

- *Online Payment Gateway:*

Krush Seva integrates security features into its online payment gateway that allows users to pay for services hassle-free. This ensures that financial transactions are safe, fast and hassle-free.

- *Speed:*

The website offers fast loading times and performance, allowing farmers to quickly access the information and services they need.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

[6]The launch of Krush Seva is a significant step forward in agriculture ecommerce. In recent years, agriculture has gradually started to use technology to provide good results to farmers. Krush Seva is a prime example of this model, which focuses on improving the supply process of pesticides and herbicides required for crop management. The ecommerce platform recognizes the specific needs of farmers who often face the challenge of assessing the quality and price of agricultural products. Krush Seva solves this problem by offering a wide range of pesticides and insecticides at competitive prices by providing a digital store for these products. This cost-effective purchasing is one of the best features of the platform, allowing farmers to get quality products without compromising their budget. Userfriendliness is another feature of Krush Seva. Its userfriendly interface allows farmers to easily access and purchase agricultural equipment through the digital portal. Focusing on accessibility is especially important in areas where adoption is uneven.

The platform's commitment to security is also notable. With strict data protection and secure online payment options, Krush Seva increases the trust of its users by creating a secure environment for financial transactions and personal information. Additionally, the platform's emphasis on providing valuable information and advice for product management sets it apart from others. Farmers can access valuable information and advice to make informed decisions about their crop care needs. It is particularly useful to have market information and weather forecasts available; It allows farmers to improve their marketing strategies and adjust their operations according to the weather.

IV. MODULES / USERS / STAKEHOLDERS

A. Modules of Krush- Seva:

- *Service Module:*

- Utility Bill Payments.
- Certificate Issuance (Birth, Death, Income, etc.).
- Tax Payments (Property Tax, Goods and Services Tax, etc.).

- Licensing and Permits.
- Government Exam Registrations.

- *Payment Gateway Module:*

- Secure Online Payment Processing.
- Integration with Multiple Payment Methods (Credit/Debit Cards, Net Banking, Mobile Wallets)

- *Document Verification Module:*

- Digital Submission of Documents
- Verification and Authentication of Submitted Documents

- *Communication Module:*

- Government-to-Citizen Notifications
- Alerts for Application Status Updates
- Citizen Feedback and Query Resolution

B. Krush-Seva Users:

- *Citizens: -*

Persons with online access to government services, payment and certificate.

- *Key Personnel: -*

Managers who manage the platform, monitor service requests and ensure timely service. 3) Service Providers: Many government institutions and organizations (such as electricity offices, municipal companies, health directorates) providing services through this platform.

C. Stakeholders of Krush-Seva:

- *Citizens:*

Key stakeholders benefit from valuable, efficient and transparent services.

- *Government of Justice:*

Stakeholders who oversee the use, maintenance and development of E-Mitra services.

- *Service Provider:*

Participants participate in digital services and ensure integration with the E-Mitra platform.

- *Financial Institutions:*

Participants providing secure payment gateways and financial services for E-Mitra business.

- *Entrepreneurs and Businesses:*

Participants benefit from easy authorization, authorization and registration processes that promote business and economic development.

D. Figures and Tables

Fig 2 DFD Level-2(Agri Management)

E. Algorithm

- Step 1: Users register with Krushi Seva by entering their name, email, phone number and farm address.
- Step 2: After registration, the user will automatically log in and receive the login information via email or SMS.
- Step 3: Users enter the website and search for pesticides, antibiotics, botanicals, etc. Searches for products including.
- Step 4: The user selects the product he wants and adds it to the shopping cart.
- Step 5: The user evaluates the shopping cart and proceeds to the payment process.
- Step 6: User pays securely online for the selected product.
- Step 7: The user receives an order confirmation with payment details.
- Step 8: The system prepares the shipment.
- Step 9: Notify the user of the estimated delivery date and get tracking information.
- Step 10: The order will be sent to the farm provided by the user.

F. Pros & Cons

➤ Pros of Krushi -Seva :

- Convenience: Krushi Seva offers a convenient way for farmers to access agricultural products, especially pesticides and herbicides, without the need to travel to physical stores.
- Cost-Effective Sourcing: The platform provides cost-effective sourcing, allowing farmers to compare prices and choose products that fit their budget while maintaining quality.

- User-Friendly Interface: Krushi Seva's user-friendly design ensures that even farmers with limited digital literacy can easily navigate and make purchases.
- Diverse Product Range: It offers a comprehensive range of agricultural supplies, making it a one-stop destination for farmers' needs.
- Information Resources: The platform provides valuable information and expert advice on crop management, market trends, and weather updates.
- Community Engagement: Farmers can engage with fellow farmers through forums, sharing experiences and knowledge.
- Mobile Accessibility: Krushi Seva's mobile app ensures that farmers can access services on the go, improving accessibility.

➤ Cons of Krushi- Seva:

- Internet Access: Availability of the service depends on reliable internet access, it can be limited in some rural areas.
- Digital Literacy: Farmers with limited digital literacy might find the platform challenging to use.
- Data Privacy: Concerns about data privacy and security may deter some users from making online transactions.
- Dependence on Technology: Overreliance on the platform could potentially reduce face-to-face interactions between farmers and local suppliers.
- Language Barriers: Accessibility may be limited for farmers who do not speak the primary language used on the platform.
- Delivery delays: Depending on the delivery, delivery may be delayed, which may affect farmers' schedules.

V. CONCLUSION

Overall, Krushi Seva has emerged as a key player in the digital transformation of agriculture by focusing on improving the supply process for pesticide and herbicide lines. This ecommerce solution solves a problem farmers have been facing for a long time, providing customers with quality, cost-effective and safe solutions that make the difference between cheap and good.

Krushi Seva is committed to providing valuable information and advice on crop management, economic information and weather forecasting to enable farmers to farm. The platform supports the agricultural community by providing easy and affordable access to agricultural products, especially in regions where access to digital is limited. Despite issues with digital literacy and information privacy, the potential of Krushi Seva to promote agriculture in the digital age is undeniable. It is a beacon of hope, giving farmers the tools they need to increase productivity, improve resources, and secure the world. The field is changing rapidly.

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